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Table of Contents

Project information	1
Deliverable information	1
Document information.....	1
Executive Summary	2
Introduction.....	3
Pre-pandemic operations.....	3
Significant changes to RI operations	4
Impacts of change	5
Conclusions.....	6
Appendix 1 - Stakeholder Survey responses	7

Executive Summary

The [eRImote](#) project brings together several national, and cross-national, Research Infrastructure (RI) organisations to develop recommendations for further developments of remote access to services, considering the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

This report provides a landscape overview, drawing on scenarios where RIs have changed from physical to remote access in their main service provision, but also information from RIs that were predominantly operating remote services pre-COVID, and from RIs that made a limited transition because of the pandemic.

Prior to the pandemic remote access was a limited RI delivery model, primarily adopted by data-centric services. The extent to which RIs were ready for, preparing, or considering, changes to access models was varied.

Restrictions on movement of people were universally the driver for changes to access models, but solutions developed had to be established in unusual circumstances; taking into account external factors beyond those which would have ‘ordinarily’ required consideration in such a change.

Adoption of hitherto unused remote/digital access solutions was universally achievable, but the extent was inconsistent across individual RIs, with marked sectoral differences across scientific domains.

The nature of research support activity in different scientific domains presented fundamentally varied challenges, therefore deeper exploration of how best to enable increased remote access must be conducted across domains.

Introduction

This initial review will focus on the specific situations where RIs have changed from physical to remote access in their main service provision. Information from RIs which were predominantly remote pre-COVID and from RIs which have made a limited transition will also be examined in order to draw from the widest experience.

The eRImote project comprises eight Research Infrastructure (RI) partners who cover a wide range of scientific domains: life sciences; environmental sciences; physical sciences and engineering; social and cultural sciences. Each partner organization has a role in service operation that has experienced changes to models of access because of the COVID-19 pandemic. This report summarises the findings of a range of engagement activities undertaken during 2022/23 to establish the broad landscape of remote access solutions that have developed because of these changes.

The primary engagement has been through a direct survey of eRImote partners, with learning augmented by additional intelligence gathered through three workshops conducting in Autumn'22 /Spring '23 (Task 3.2).

Pre-pandemic operations

Prior to the disruption to movement caused by the pandemic, a variety of remote access models were in place across RIs. These access models had developed over time, largely because of practical and legislative requirements and bound by available resources.

Prior to the pandemic, the extent of remote/digital access varied significantly across RIs, with the respective science domain in which the RI operated typically the defining factor of the access routes which were available.

RIs which supported purely computational or data-driven research were typically providing a high degree of remote and/or digital access prior to 2020 (c. 90%+). This incorporated a wide range of data 'archive' or digital 'repository' type organisations, which enabled secondary reuse of data previously generated either for research, or other administrative purposes. There were some situations where, in spite of the technical potential for remote access, there was a requirement for on-site access to data at RIs, or for geographical limitations on access (e.g., remote access possible, but from defined workplace locations, limited to access from a location within a specific country or region). The primary rationale for this would typically be restrictions dictated by data owners and usually related to

confidence about data security (regardless of the demonstrable issues that existed). However, in general, a large number of these RIs were providing remote/digital access to their services and doing so extensively.

At the same point in time, RIs working in the physical sciences were typically providing far fewer opportunities for remote and/or digital access (c. 20-30%). Within this domain the relevant research activity would be far more likely to require some degree of direct physical access to tangible resources, and therefore at least some of the research activity was commonly undertaken directly at a facility by a researcher, a team of researchers, or a collaborative team including both researchers and RI staff. The nature of tangible resources varies dependent on the specifics of the research activity but can include specific scientific equipment, as well as sample material or other items subject to scientific methods or necessary within the research lifecycle.

All of the RIs who provided direct information to this survey about their pre-pandemic arrangements also indicated that their delivery was consistent with their overall understanding of the norms within their relevant sector(s).

Significant changes to RI operations

Regardless of the extent of remote access prior to the pandemic, RIs typically report *at least* cross-national user communities (within the partners engaged in eRImote this typically manifested as pan-European), and report commonly servicing users globally.

From early 2020 onwards, limitations on travel, and wide-ranging guidance, or requirement, to work from home where possible, made onsite access impractical for large swathes of the user community. Consequently, this impacted the ability of researchers to access RIs, even where high levels of digital/remote access were an established method of access.

As a response, RIs began to explore rapidly how to make changes to service delivery models, and began to adapt their operational delivery. Preparedness for the changes required was variable across individual RIs.

Reflecting on the period 2020/21, as that which was most disrupted by the pandemic, no RI reported a reduction in the extent of remote/digital access, all RI with a high pre-existing level of remote/digital access reported at least maintaining that level. RIs with low levels of remote/digital access reported *at least a doubling* of the extent of remote/digital service delivery.

Of the RIs surveyed for this report, all of those that had low levels of remote/digital access prior to the pandemic, moved to increase remote/digital access. The reported extent of this transformation was highly varied. However, no RI surveyed reported a complete inability to transform access channels to allow some degree of service continuation.

Where RIs already had high levels of remote/digital access, this persisted during the pandemic, albeit with reports of initial disruption. Pre-existing remote/digital access solutions did not necessarily account for home-working, and in many cases these arrangements were predicated on access from

institutional locations (i.e., specific workplaces). Consequently, even where technical solutions existed - and had already been successfully used - work was still needed to re-establish acceptable access arrangements. Some arrangements established on this basis were temporary due to pandemic restrictions, and not necessarily permanent commitments to shift to remote/digital access.

In some circumstances, the imperative to support COVID-19 relevant research activity was an underlying facilitator in enabling change to occur. This was a supporting factor in enabling change; however, there is potential longer-term consequence insofar as these changes may be viewed as 'temporary', either by the service provider, RI funders, or other relevant stakeholders (e.g., bodies with decision making capacity about the assets deployed by the RI).

The practical implementation of remote/digital access comprised a range of challenges, which span from relatively common across RIs regardless of scientific domain, to challenges particularly distinct to the area of scientific operation.

Within RIs primarily supporting data-driven research, relatively few aspects of operation required fundamental rework and many of the necessary changes related to the adaption or renegotiation of pre-existing governance and compliance solutions. Established policies and procedures which already enabled remote/digital access commonly needed amending, however a basis for arrangements was typically in place. Challenges often related to confidence of data security and how to best provide continued assurance to external bodies (e.g., data depositors; data controllers; accrediting bodies) whilst accommodating new ways of working and restrictions on access institutional workplaces and/or devices.

Within RIs supporting physical science, especially given the lesser extent of pre-existing remote/digital research challenges, more fundamental redesign was needed in some cases. Challenges included more significant change to the roles of RI staff and how they related to, and worked with, researchers during the delivery of individual research project activity. Practical issues, such as access to facilities, machinery and instrumentation, also had to be addressed.

From even an initial review of practice across a limited number of RIs it is apparent that 'remote' and 'digital' cannot be used interchangeably, or synonymously, as clear descriptors of the nature of service access, or the types of change desired or required.

Impacts of change

As a consideration of the sole purpose of RI existence, no decrease in the quality of science conducted was identified across the RIs surveyed. Awareness of satisfaction of service users was largely unknown to the RIs surveyed. However, RIs generally reported that the effort of access for users had decreased. A range of benefits for users, as a result of increased remote/digital access, could be identified by RIs, included removing barriers to access (e.g. accommodating non-COVID limitations on travel, such as child-care responsibilities; the cost to users of travel to specific locations for access etc.).

All RIs, with little correlation of the overall extent of a move to remote/digital access provision, indicated an increase in workload in the RI. Where a distinction existed, this increase was primarily focused on the 'service providers/RI staff' as a 'strong increase' rather than elements on an RI which constituted the 'RI hub/central office'. Satisfaction of service provider/RI staff was reported to vary across RIs, however increases/decreases were noted to be slight rather than significant in every instance.

Several of the RIs surveyed did not report a clear understanding of variation of levels of satisfaction, of either staff or users, indicating that development of measures of service satisfaction relating to changing modes of access may be a valuable exercise to pursue.

Conclusions

There are two primary challenges associated with an initial systematic review of changes in remote access practice, one definitional and the other emerging from the scope of the eRImote project. It is clear that "remote access" means significantly different things to the "hard sciences" community, where it is understood broadly to mean non-geolocated access to physical resources such as instrumentation, and the "data services" community, where non-geolocated access to information resources such as downloading datasets, has been the norm for several decades. One possible approach to dealing with these two different paradigms is to approach them as a spectrum of use cases, where the incremental differentiator would be distance of the actor from the resource. Our recommended alternative approach is to consider whether these two paradigms are so substantively distinct that they should be treated, for the purposes of analysis and investigation, as two separate arenas of "remote access" in the green paper, rather than inducing artificial commonalities.

The second challenge relates to the breadth of domains and disciplinary specialisms under analysis in eRImote. It is rather obvious that, for example, social sciences and structural biologists will have domain-specific practices, subject matter concerns and often very different infrastructures. It is our recommendation that in considering "remote access" within the scope of eRImote, we should progress towards a more cross-domain *lingua franca* in year 2 to support more meaningful discussion in a number of areas, particularly infrastructure and process analysis. In practice, this means developing a number of typologies (if not formal ontologies), especially in areas like services, digital objects and consumer types (or actors), that would constitute a set of common reference points for cross-domain discussion.

Appendix 1 - Stakeholder Survey responses

The stakeholder survey deployed to gather feedback for this report received nine responses. These responses came from eight organisations:

1. DESY / LEAPS
2. Irish Social Science Data Archive
3. CESSDA-ERIC
4. FORS
5. EMSO-ERIC
6. INPA / INTERACT
7. Instruct-ERIC
8. Euro-BioImaging-ERIC.